

ELASTIC Newsletter

(July 2024 – May 2025)

About the project

The ELASTIC project aims to enable secure, efficient, and scalable service orchestration for next-generation 6G networks. By leveraging technologies such as Function-as-a-Service (FaaS), WebAssembly, and IoT, ELASTIC will deliver an open-source framework supporting serverless deployment, dynamic scaling, and advanced security across distributed infrastructures.

The project brings together 13 partners from 8 countries—including universities, research institutes, SMEs, and industry leaders—combining expertise in edge computing, cybersecurity, cloud infrastructure, and telecommunications.

Project Overview

The ELASTIC project has made strong progress during its first year, advancing secure and efficient orchestration of services across the compute continuum. Research and development work has focused on trusted WebAssembly modules, confidential computing, and developer-friendly tooling for 6G networks.

ELASTIC Team
Ghent, Belgium

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Plenary Meeting in Ghent

February 2025

Hosted by IMEC, the meeting brought together all partners to reflect on the first year of technical and collaborative progress. It featured detailed reviews of each work package, identified key areas for improvement, and outlined the roadmap for the second year, including integration milestones, pilot activities, and standardization priorities.

The sessions also addressed cross-cutting themes such as security integration, performance validation, and stakeholder engagement, reinforcing a shared commitment to delivering a robust and impactful ELASTIC platform.

News & Highlights

Press Release: ELASTIC Marks One Year Advancing Secure 6G Service Orchestration

April 2025

A public update marked ELASTIC's first year, outlining achievements in platform design and cross-partner collaboration. The statement previewed the upcoming pilot phase and testing roadmap.

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ELASTIC Expert Advisory Board Kick-Off

March 2025, Online

ELASTIC held its first advisory board meeting with external experts to gather feedback on project direction and exploitation opportunities. The session confirmed alignment with stakeholder needs and provided useful input for the next phase.

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IMEC Presents ELASTIC WebAssembly Research at WasmCon 2024

November 2024, Salt Lake City, USA

IMEC shared ELASTIC insights with the WebAssembly community, focusing on trust, portability, and runtime integration. These efforts helped position ELASTIC within key developer and standardization groups.

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Telefónica I+D presented ELASTIC at SETN 2024 Conference

September 2024, Athens, Greece

ELASTIC shared its work on responsible AI at the SETN 2024 conference in Athens. The session underlined ELASTIC's approach to fairness, transparency, and trust in orchestration models.

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Upcoming Presence at EuCNC & 6G Summit 2025

ELASTIC will participate in the **EuCNC & 6G Summit 2025**, taking place from June 3–6 in Poznan, Poland. The project will be featured at **Booth #12**, where partners will present **live demonstrations** of secure edge computing solutions developed during the first year. Visitors will have the opportunity to **engage with the ELASTIC team**, explore the **technical innovations**, and learn about the project's vision for **future 6G networks**.

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Women in STEAM Campaign

This year, ELASTIC launched its "Women Driving ELASTIC" series, profiling contributions of female professionals in the project:

- **Despina Kopanaki (TUC)** on leadership and diversity
- **Dhouha Ayed (THALES)** on cybersecurity and innovation
- **Jelena Vasic (Zentrix Lab)** on communication and impact

The campaign aimed to highlight the value of diverse expertise in **shaping ELASTIC's outcomes**, and to encourage **visibility of women in advanced tech fields**.

Events

Throughout the year, ELASTIC engaged with the research community and broader stakeholders through several high-impact events. These provided opportunities to showcase results, exchange knowledge, and contribute to technical discussions on AI, cybersecurity, and 6G orchestration.

AI & Security Webinar
(Apr 2025)

Joint event with EU-funded projects addressing how AI enhances network security and how to secure AI models in future networks. The webinar promoted knowledge-sharing across multiple R&D initiatives and identified key future challenges.

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CyberHOT Summer School
(Upcoming event)

ELASTIC supports the 2025 edition of the cybersecurity training event in Crete, focusing on hands-on learning for researchers and professionals.

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Contributing to the Scientific Community

- **"Exploring Crisis-Driven Social Media Patterns"**: Presents a curated Twitter dataset and analysis of user behavior during the Russo-Ukrainian war.
- **"Securing Stack Smashing Protection in WebAssembly"**: Enhances memory safety in WebAssembly applications through compiler and hardware-based solutions.
- **"Secure Unikernels for Serverless Computing"**: Demonstrates how unikernels can improve isolation and performance in cloud-edge deployments.
- **"Demystifying Privacy in 5G Standalone Networks"**: Analyzes privacy mechanisms and limitations in current 5G SA network implementations. Presents a curated dataset on Twitter usage during the Russo-Ukrainian war.

All ELASTIC publications are available on the project website

Next Steps

As ELASTIC enters its second year, the focus will shift toward refining and testing the integrated platform in real-world pilots. Technical development will continue across orchestration, runtime security, and standardization activities, with a growing emphasis on validating use cases and maximizing the impact of the project's results.

ELASTIC will also maintain its engagement with the wider research and industrial community through active participation in events, targeted dissemination, and collaboration with other European projects.

ELASTIC Consortium

Keep in touch with us!

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